

Performance of 5460ps in Fujian, China, 1988.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Exserted stigma (%)	Resistance score				
							Blast	Bacterial blight	Brown planthopper	Bacterial leaf streak	Grassy stunt
5460ps	125	76.5	13.6	108.3	23.0	46.2	1	1	2	3	3
IR54	150	90.0	11.7	121.0	23.1	42.3	1	1	2	3	3

5460ps has high resistance to major diseases and insects, high-yielding agrocharacters, and good quality. Its

floral characters influencing outcrossing are also good (see table).

The critical stage of sterility-

transformation is about 10 Jul and fertility-transformation 10 Sep under conditions in Fuzhou (26°N). □

New japonica hybrid developed in China

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76-27A/PC312, a newly developed long-duration (130 d) japonica cross, has erect flag leaves, large panicles, and heavy grain. It shows moderate resistance to blast and bacterial blight. It has 90-cm plant height, 125 spikelets/panicle, and 70-80% seed set. A thousand grains weigh 26 g.

In yield trials in 1985 in 8 locations in northern Hunan, it averaged 6.3 t/ha (see table), 11.3% more than check Aiking 23. In farmers' fields in Shang-Tan in 1986, it outyielded Shan-you 63.

Seed production for the combination is easy; no split sowing is needed. It can yield 3 t hybrid seeds/ha. It is suitable for intermediate-fertility soils, for both single- or double-cropping seasons. □

Yield performance of japonica hybrid at 8 locations in Hunan, China, 1985.

Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD	
	Hybrid ^a	Check	At 5%	At 1%
Changde	6.3	6.05	0.4	0.5
Yueyang	5.5	5.24	0.4	0.6
Miluo	6.5**	5.61	0.5	0.7
Taojiang	5.3	4.83	0.5	0.7
Xihu	7.4**	6.85	0.4	0.6
Huarong	6.3**	5.98	0.9	0.9
Wangcheng	6.8	6.23	0.3	0.6
Changsha	6.4**	4.62	1.4	1.6
Av	6.3**	5.68		

^a** = significant at 1%.

Effects of storage on rice germplasm viability

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In most breeding programs that lack storage facilities, germplasm is

maintained by periodical regeneration. Growing out all germplasm accessions every year takes extensive resources. We studied genotypic differences in germination under conventional storage conditions over 30 mo, to identify genotypes that retain viability longer.

Seeds of 24 varieties were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center in Nov 1984. Initial germination

Table 1. Ranges and means of temperature and relative humidity during storage, CRURRS, Hazaribag, India.

Month	Year	Relative humidity (%)		Temperature (°C)	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Nov	1984	12 - 93	63.23 ± 1.87	7.0 - 29.0	19.50 ± 0.40
Dec	1984	14 - 88	52.31 ± 1.23	5.0 - 28.0	16.77 ± 0.24
Jan	1985	31 - 100	72.40 ± 2.25	7.0 - 27.0	16.35 ± 0.25
Feb	1985	32 - 100	63.02 ± 1.54	5.0 - 29.0	17.63 ± 0.28
Mar	1985	50 - 91	76.40 ± 1.18	13.0 - 38.0	25.64 ± 0.35
Apr	1985	28 - 84	57.42 ± 1.47	18.0 - 41.0	29.80 ± 0.37
May	1985	28 - 100	66.05 ± 1.83	20.0 - 43.0	30.27 ± 0.46
Jun	1985	55 - 100	84.67 ± 2.41	22.5 - 40.8	30.59 ± 0.37
Jul	1985	90 - 100	95.13 ± 0.52	22.1 - 32.0	26.25 ± 0.23
Aug	1985	88 - 100	96.03 ± 0.63	22.8 - 32.8	26.96 ± 0.24
Sep	1985	82 - 100	94.23 ± 0.92	21.8 - 32.2	26.40 ± 0.14
Oct	1985	87 - 100	84.23 ± 1.92	14.5 - 32.5	24.04 ± 0.50
Nov	1985	35 - 90	74.70 ± 2.02	10.4 - 28.0	20.19 ± 0.35
Dec	1985	53 - 100	79.56 ± 2.16	8.3 - 26.1	17.62 ± 0.36
Jan	1986	46 - 95	63.81 ± 1.83	5.9 - 26.5	16.31 ± 0.47
Feb	1986	44 - 94	62.29 ± 1.98	10.0 - 30.2	19.12 ± 0.30
Mar	1986	24 - 63	47.20 ± 1.83	13.9 - 39.5	24.92 ± 0.5 1
Apr	1986	29 - 71	48.97 ± 1.73	18.3 - 40.0	29.72 ± 0.38
May	1986	37 - 100	58.19 ± 2.59	19.5 - 40.0	29.42 ± 0.31
Jun	1986	35 - 96	70.73 ± 4.12	22.5 - 41.5	29.84 ± 0.63
Jul	1986	66 - 95	82.68 ± 1.25	22.4 - 32.3	26.04 ± 0.27
Aug	1986	65 - 92	81.23 ± 1.38	22.4 - 33.2	26.72 ± 0.18
Sep	1986	65 - 95	81.27 ± 1.72	20.0 - 33.3	26.07 ± 0.44
Oct	1986	41 - 100	79.44 ± 1.19	17.0 - 31.0	24.73 ± 0.29
Nov	1986	50 - 90	70.07 ± 1.68	13.5 - 29.5	21.41 ± 0.38
Dec	1986	53 - 94	71.03 ± 1.72	8.8 - 24.5	16.93 ± 0.26
Jan	1987	49 - 75	62.58 ± 1.40	6.9 - 24.3	15.67 ± 0.34
Feb	1987	56 - 68	61.29 ± 0.74	10.1 - 30.0	20.25 ± 0.37
Mar	1987	45 - 71	55.52 ± 1.20	14.0 - 35.8	24.36 ± 0.47
Apr	1987	37 - 15	52.03 ± 1.72	18.0 - 39.3	29.02 ± 0.34
May	1987	42 - 80	53.52 ± 1.85	18.5 - 41.0	30.54 ± 0.64